

“ART-AUCTION” CONCEPT AND WORLD EXPERIENCE IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the activities of galleries and auctions that reflect the currently developing art and marketing fields. Also, during the research, the differences and similarities characteristic of this type of activity in the world and in our country have been noted. In this regard, a project on the development of this type of activity in our country has been proposed.*

Keywords: *art market, art auction, art galleries, sale of antiques.*

Currently, there are two players in the global art market, one is leaders and private galleries, and the other is auction houses. This type of business is very conservative and maintains elitism (the function of meeting the demands of the elite layer of society) in today's era of online galleries and auctions.

Art and collectibles auctions can be considered the most popular part of the art business in society. Some of the leading auction brands are embodying marketing innovations around the world. This is reflected in the achievements of high culture in the financial and intellectual spheres, the flow of information (the development of Internet gadgets) and many other aspects.

There are several types of auctions in the world. The most popular are the English auction for raising rates and the Dutch auction for lowering rates. Almost all auctions in the art segment are organized according to the English style. It depends on many factors. First of all, the historical aspect plays a big role. Dutch auctions are "quiet" and "quick", requiring concentration and lightning-fast reactions. This type of auction is used in the sale of "perishable" goods, for example, in the flower market in the Netherlands or in the fish market in Japan.

As for the history of trade in art and antiques, it is known that its roots go back to ancient Rome. To date, European auction houses are the first established commercial trading houses in the world. Stockholm Auction House is one of the largest trading houses in Sweden and was founded in 1674. Among the leaders of the art market established in the 18th century, we can list the well-known and famous Christie's, Sotheby's, Bonhams, Dorotheum and Phillips.

By the age of "Enlightenment" collecting becomes popular. Later, it will focus mainly on numismatics, engravings, "cabinet" and library collections of books and minerals. Therefore, the auction houses that appeared at this time primarily specialized in the sale of books and engravings. A little later, in the second half of the 18th century, the collection of paintings led to the formation of the direction of social thought, i.e. art criticism.

The main organizations where works of art are priced are famous auction houses. Works of art are offered for sale along with various antiques at auction houses such as Christie's, Sotheby's, Bonhams, Dorotheum, MacDougall's, Stockholm Auction House. The initial price set for them is determined after the history of its previous sales and evaluations of art experts and critics. Famous works of art are often sold for several times their original price when they are in high demand.

"Buying art at auction is very different from buying art at a gallery. At auctions, prices are transparent, all bids are open, and the highest bidder wins the artwork. In galleries, the process of purchasing an item and the price of the item may be more uncertain. It can be assumed that these two outlets will always be in competition. Nevertheless, sometimes the goals of galleries and auction houses coincide, and outlets work together. Their cooperation is, in fact, an integral part of the art market.

While galleries discover, exhibit, and create a collector for their artists, they can channel their artists' work into a secondary market of their own interest. Galleries and auction houses sometimes work together to check the authenticity of old works and consult with each other about provenance. However, these relationships often mean more, especially in secondary market sales".

Works of art are evaluated according to several criteria. First of all, the popularity of the author or his position in a certain art direction is taken into account.

At the same time, the work is evaluated by the period in which it was painted, what adventures it experienced, and how much it influenced the history of art. Also, which art movement or style it belongs to affects the value of the work.

The breadth of content horizons, diversity of creative styles in the work of masters of fine and applied arts, establishing wide connections and finding their place in the field of world culture is a sign of the high culture of our country and the roots of its art going back to a long history. With these features, it has found a worthy place in the world and has been captivating art lovers. Also, in Uzbekistan, the importance of visual and practical art in establishing cultural relations between the embassies of countries on all continents of the world with our country is incomparable, and its creators are taking the lead in this regard.

In recent years, one after another, it has become a tradition to organize art exhibitions of outstanding works of fine and applied art of our country and unique collections of museums of our country in foreign countries.

At the same time, the works presented at the exhibitions are an artistic representation of the beauty of our country and its people, the skills of artists, their achievements, and the level of culture and art of our country, which can be understood by foreign viewers without any translator.

Taking these achievements into account, the reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan can be evaluated as efforts to develop art and economy and bring it to the world market.

In 2023, one of the 5 main directions of the state program for the implementation of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the year 2023, the year of care for human and quality education, is to ensure moral development and the new sector "ART VERNISSAGE" auction house was established in order to popularize the visual and applied art of Uzbekistan at the international level and to organize art galleries and art residencies.

On November 30, the auction house "ART VERNISSAGE" held an auction entitled "Cultural heritage of the masters of applied arts of Uzbekistan". The auction featured numismatics (coins of Somonii, Sufis, Amir Timur era), porcelain and marble plates, obdastas and other copper items, carpets, suzanes, silk robes, horse saddles. Each work of applied art is examined by the art critic and appraiser experts of the appraisal company "ART APPRAISAL CENTER" for its originality, antiquity, suitability for the work of art, appraisal reports are prepared and insured by the insurance company "APEX".

It is noteworthy that representatives of Christie's auction house, one of the 2 largest auction houses in the world with a 300-year history, focused on selling world-famous works of art,

participated in the auction. This can be seen as an important step in the formation of the art market of Uzbekistan.

One of the main goals of the "Art Vernissage" auction house is to organize exhibitions and auctions of the works of artists of Uzbekistan, and the opportunity to see and buy the works of artists of Uzbekistan in any country of the world.

Evaluation of auctions is carried out in a two-stage process based on international experience and national legislation. In this process, a methodology based on international experience was developed and approved together with partner organizations in accordance with the law.

But it should be noted that this is a big news for Uzbekistan, which has not had an art market until now. Therefore, the system of evaluation of works has not been established consistently. The establishment of the "Art Appraisal Center" evaluation organization together with the "Art Vernissage" trading house allows to evaluate works of art in our republic on a full scientific theoretical basis. Works of art are important not only as works of art, but also as an economic base.

For many years, the market of works of art did not develop and was not formed due to the lack of methods of evaluation of works of art and evaluation organizations in the republic.

The auction house located in Tashkent includes:

- publishing house;
- art appraisal company "Art Appraisal Center";
- art gallery
- there is a special laboratory that carries out technological examination of works of art.

This achievement can be considered as the first step in the development of the art market of Uzbekistan.

As another step in the process of organizing art auctions in Uzbekistan, within the framework of the "World Youth Festival", the Youth Affairs Agency in cooperation with the "Kind Hands" foundation, AVO Bank and We Digital marketing agency, held the first unique exhibition of the project called "Orzu".

"Orzu" is a special combination of human creativity and artificial intelligence. Works created based on the impressions of blind children are presented at the exhibition. These pictures are not just pictures, but a reflection of children's deep and impressive thoughts and imaginations.

At the exhibition, 20 artworks created by artificial intelligence and rendered on paper by artists from "Sharm Studio" were showcased.

At the exhibition, 20 pictures created by artificial intelligence, written on paper by "Sharm Studio" artists, were shown.

The proceeds from the creative works sold at the charity exhibition were directed to operations to restore the sight of blind children.

Also, the uniqueness of the integration in this direction was that the possibility of donating funds for the project through the Payme, Click and Payze payment services also makes it convenient for everyone. It has attracted more than 3,000 visitors, including international visitors from Russia, USA, Turkey, China, Australia, South Korea, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Kuwait, France and Germany.

All paintings were successfully sold in this auction. A total of 151,400,000 soums (about \$12,000) was collected. The prices for paintings ranged from 4 million to 20 million soums, said the organizers of the event.

The most expensive painting at the auction was bought by Mr. I, a Chinese tourist. "This picture shows high mountains and waterfalls. This is a symbol of friendship in my country. That's why I bought it even at the highest price," said the Chinese guest, happy to receive the picture.

At the auction of artworks held within the framework of the exhibition, former pediatric surgeon Mahmud Asomov actively participated and purchased two creative pieces. He bought the painting "Aspiration Towards Dreams" for 6 million soums and the piece titled "Paths of Life" for 8 million soums. "If these paintings had cost 20 million soums, I would still have bought them, because they are not just simple sketches made with a brush. The paintings represent the dreams and aspirations of children who cannot see the world in all its colors."

"The team of specialists gathered facts and elements about the imaginative world of children and adolescents and compiled them into a text. The collected information was fed into artificial intelligence, which transformed the inner world of children into virtual images. After that, the images created by artificial intelligence were turned into paintings by artists," says Hikmatilla Ubaydullayev, one of the main idea's authors.

This project, which combines art and technology, allows visually impaired and low-vision children to express their perceptions of the world through creative works and drawings created with the help of artificial intelligence. For many children with visual impairments, sharing their inner world through creativity is an important way to develop their abilities and establish social connections.

The project emphasizes the importance of inclusivity and equality in society, vividly illustrating the talents and capabilities of children with visual impairments.

The inaugural art auctions and charity auctions serve to elevate the spiritual culture of Uzbekistan's citizens and expand the community of art enthusiasts and curious individuals, contributing to the increasing number of such events.

As mentioned earlier, the primary venues for valuing artworks globally are renowned auction houses. Various artifacts, along with artworks, are auctioned at houses like Christie's, Sotheby's, Bonhams, Doroteum, MacDougall's, and Stockholm Auction House. The starting price set for these pieces is determined based on their previous sales history and evaluations from art experts and critics. If there is high demand for famous artworks, they can sell for several times their starting price.

In this context, let's briefly outline the history of the establishment of one of the world-renowned auction houses, Sotheby's.

Founded in 1744, Sotheby's is one of the world's most famous art and luxury auction houses. Sotheby's promotes access to and ownership of rare art and luxury objects through auctions and buy-it-now channels, including private sales, e-commerce and retail. Sotheby's trusted global marketplace is supported by an industry-leading technology platform and a network of experts in 40 countries and 70 categories, including contemporary art, modern and impressionist art, old masters, Chinese works of art, Jewelry, Watches, Wine & Spirits, and Design, also covers collectible cars and real estate. Sotheby's believes in the transformative power of arts and culture and is committed to making our industries more inclusive, sustainable and collaborative.

The founder of Sotheby's, Samuel Baker, an entrepreneur, first a publisher and a successful bookseller, held his first auction under his own name on March 11, 1744.

For a long time, auction houses and galleries have been an integral part of the European art market, serving as centers for showcasing artistic talent, facilitating sales, and preserving cultural heritage. From major auction houses in London to avant-garde galleries in Paris, these institutions have shaped the dynamics of the art world over the centuries.

In Europe, prominent auction houses like Sotheby's, Christie's, and Phillips attract international attention with their prestigious sales of visual art, antiques, and collections. Each house has its unique selling points, clientele, and specializations that contribute to the diverse ecosystem of the art market.

Sotheby's CEO - Charles Stewart said: "We are technologically equipped to manage our business in different scenarios. We are confident that we can continue to provide excellent service and sales to our customers around the world as our customers increasingly engage with us in digital formats to discover, learn and bid on art and objects."

The tradition of creating mobile applications introduced as a requirement of the day is becoming more popular day by day. With this goal in mind, Sotheby's has taken a number of measures to develop the application. The Sotheby's app is a mobile app designed to enhance the experience of art collectors, connoisseurs and bidders. Some key features and functions of the Sotheby's app include:

1. **Trades and Auctions:** Users can participate in live and online auctions through the app. This includes placing bids in real-time, receiving notifications of auction updates, and tracking multiple interests.

2. **Catalog Access:** The app provides access to auction catalogs, allowing users to browse upcoming sales, view detailed descriptions, and view high-quality images of artworks and items available for bidding.

3. **Personalized Alerts:** Users can set up alerts for specific lots, auctions or categories of interest, ensuring they are notified of relevant events and opportunities.

4. **Virtual Viewing Rooms:** The app often features virtual exhibitions where users can explore artworks in a digital format, providing an immersive experience.

5. **Account Management:** Users can manage their Sotheby's accounts through the app, including tracking bid history, managing payment methods and updating personal information.

6. **News & Insights:** The app features articles, videos and insights on the art market, trends and Sotheby's events, keeping users up to date with the latest developments in the art world.

7. **User-friendly interface:** The app is designed to be intuitive and easy to navigate, making it accessible to both experienced collectors and newcomers to the art market.

Based on the sources studied during this research, it has been concluded that there is a need to develop a modern mobile application aimed at enhancing the experience of art collectors, enthusiasts, and participants in auction houses in Uzbekistan. This application will feature an intuitive interface showcasing a catalog of various artworks filled with high-quality images and detailed descriptions. Users will benefit from real-time bidding opportunities, secure payment options, and customized notifications for upcoming auctions. Additionally, the app will include educational resources related to art collections and community features to increase user engagement. By integrating these elements, our application aims to create a seamless and enriching platform that connects art enthusiasts and enhances their auction experience in Uzbekistan.

This will signify the integration of Uzbekistan's art market into the global art market. The mobile application is designed not only to simplify the auction process but also to foster the development of the live art enthusiast community in Uzbekistan. By providing educational resources and engagement tools, we hope to make the auction experience enjoyable and convenient while enhancing users' understanding and appreciation of art.

We offer a user-friendly mobile application aimed at facilitating artistic auctions in Uzbekistan. The app improves user experience by providing easy access to artworks, real-time bidding, secure payments, and community participation features.

Advantages:

- Simplifies the auction process for users;
- Expands the auction house's reach to a broader audience;
- Cultivates a community of art enthusiasts.

Various events related to the monumental construction projects currently underway in Uzbekistan serve as a foundation to highlight the unique pages of our great country's history. The continuous development of the arts and culture sector, as mentioned above, and the efforts being made to promote our national art and culture to the world create a basis for bringing Uzbekistan's art auction houses and their systematic development to a global level.

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